

ESTIMATED TECHNIQUES USED IN ASSESSING THE NATIONAL INCOME OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The Nigerian populace has been reading and in most cases informed about the amount generated by the nation Nigeria as income which determine the development policies toward the wellbeing of the populace. It is pertinent to consider and analysis the estimation techniques as adopted by the apex bank (Central Bank of Nigeria CBN) and other economic experts in engaging this all important factor (national income) in the economic existence and development of the nation Nigeria. This research paper sought to analyse estimated techniques in determining the national income of Nigeria. The data for this study was obtained from only secondary source. The nature of the data which are used by the researcher for this study was published secondary data. These secondary sources of data include; texts, statistics data, journals, textbooks, internet texts, and government publications. Analysis of published or secondary data shows that there are various types of estimation techniques adopted for Nigeria's national income evaluation. Findings from analysed data show that there are three distinct methods of estimating national income in Nigeria: GDP/GNP expenditure or product approach, GDP/GNP income or earning approach and GDP/GNP value added or output approach. It was concluded that the importance of calculating the national income of Nigeria cannot be over emphasized as national budget, development policies, and planning are based on the national income. Reports have shown that the Nigerian economy is recovering after the accidental COVID-19 economic attacks.

KEYWORDS: National Income, Estimated Techniques, and Central Bank of Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

National income means the value of goods and services produced by a country during a financial year (Kumar, 2018). Thus, it is the net result of all economic activities of any country during a period of one year and is valued in terms of money. National income is an uncertain term and is often used interchangeably with the national dividend, national output, and national expenditure. National Income is the total amount of income accruing to a country

from economic activities in a fixed period of time (i.e., One Year) (Kumar, 2018). It includes payments made to all resources either in the form of wages, interest, rent, and profits. The progress of a country can be determined by the growth of the national income of the country (Kumar, 2018). National income is the sum total of the value of all the goods and services manufactured by the residents of the country, in a year, within its domestic boundaries or outside (vendantu.com). It is a net amount of income of the citizens by production in a year. To be more precise, national income is the accumulated money value of all final goods and services produced in a country during one financial year. Computation of National Income is very vital as it indicates the overall health of our economy for that particular year (vedantu.com).

The aggregate economic performance of a nation is calculated with the help of National income data. According to [toppr.com](#), there are three techniques of estimating the National Income of a country, and they are from the income side, the output side and the expenditure side. According to [tradingeconomics.com](#), the gross domestic product (GDP) is the measures of national income and output for a given country's economy. The gross domestic product (GDP) is equal to the total expenditures for all final goods and services produced within the country in a stipulated period of time ([tradingeconomics.com](#)).

According to [tradingeconomics.com](#), the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Nigeria was worth 432.30 billion US dollars in 2020, according to official data from the World Bank. The Gross Domestic Product value of Nigeria represents 0.38 percent of the world economy ([tradingeconomics.com](#)). Available information and published document on Nigeria's national income are done quarterly based on the mechanism adopted by economic analysts. According to [nigerianstat.gov.ng](#), Quarterly National Accounts (QNA) are integrated system of macroeconomic accounts designed to describe the entire system of production in a nation on a quarterly basis. They provide a picture of the current economic status of the economy that is more timely and frequent than that provided by Annual National Accounts (ANA) ([nigerianstat.gov.ng](#)). The key attribute of QNA is that they provide a reasonable level of detail of the economy that help government to assess, analyse, and monitor economic growth on a regular basis ([tradingeconomics.com](#)). This seminar paper seeks to analyse the various estimated techniques used in assessing the national income of Nigeria as made public through published materials.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

There are various techniques of estimating National Income ranging from product, income and expenditure methods. The national income of Nigeria according to CBN (2021), N2,208.10 billion was federally collected revenue in the fourth quarter of 2020 which fell by 13.1 per cent and 8.3 per cent below the budget benchmark and the level in the preceding quarter. Arriving at this, the different estimated techniques were employed as published by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) (2021) to calculate the national income and present the details of the income as calculated per quarter of the year.

The Nigerian populace has been reading and in most cases informed about the amount generated by the nation Nigeria as income which determine the development policies toward the wellbeing of the populace. It is pertinent to consider and analysis the estimation techniques as adopted by the apex bank (Central Bank of Nigeria CBN) and other economic experts in

engaging this all important factor (national income) in the economic existence and development of the nation Nigeria. Against this backdrop, this seminar paper seeks to analyse estimated techniques in determining the national income of Nigeria.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The major aim of this research work is to analyse the estimated techniques of national income of Nigeria. The specific objectives are to analyse:

1. the types of estimated techniques of national income used in Nigeria
2. the importance of adopted estimated techniques of national income in Nigeria

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

National Income

National income is the sum total of the value of all the goods and services manufactured by the residents of the country, in a year, within its domestic boundaries or outside. It is a net amount of income of the citizens by production in a year (vedantu.com). To be more precise, national income is the accumulated money value of all final goods and services produced in a country during one financial year. Computation of National Income is very vital as it indicates the overall health of our economy for that particular year (vedantu.com). The aggregate economic performance of a nation is calculated with the help of National income data. The basic purpose of national income is to throw light on aggregate output and income and provide a basis for the government to formulate their policy, programmes, to maximize the national welfare of the people. Central Statistical organisation calculates the national income in India (vedantu.com).

According to Ott (2021), National Income Accounts (NIAs) are fundamental aggregate statistics in macroeconomic analysis. The ground-breaking development of national income and systems of NIAs was one of the most far-reaching innovations in applied economics in the early twentieth century. NIAs provide a quantitative basis for choosing and assessing economic policies as well as making possible quantitative macroeconomic modelling and analysis. NIAs cannot substitute for policymakers' judgment or allow them to evade policy decisions, but they do provide a basis for the objective statement and assessment of economic policies (Ott, 2021). Ott (2021) further posit that combined with population data, national income accounts can provide a measure of well-being through per capita income and its growth over time. Also, National Income Accounts, combined with labour force data, can be used to assess the level and growth rate of productivity, although the utility of such calculations is limited by National Income Accounts' omission of home production, underground activity, and illegal production. Combined with financial and monetary data, National Income Accounts provide a guide to inflation policy. National Income Accounts provide the basis for evaluating government policy and can rationalize political challenges to incumbents by people who are dissatisfied with measurable aspects of the government's policies. In emerging and transition economies, implementing a dependable and accurate system of National Income Accounts is a crucial step in developing economic policy (Ott, 2021).

National Income Accounts, to be most useful, require honest and timely publication. Long-delayed information is of no use either in making policy or in monitoring the efficacy of policies already implemented. Delay frequently implies that the government has something to hide. Indeed, once released, NIAs can enforce their own discipline. That is, obfuscation cannot be maintained by altering or exaggerating one aspect of NIAs, say investment or growth of total income, since each such number is related to others, and consistency is a check on the accuracy of the components. Because the data cannot easily be faked, autocrats are loathe to publish their countries' NIAs and either proscribe or delay their release. Turkmenistan's dictator, for example, does not report to the IMF, and the governments of Myanmar (1999) and Zimbabwe (2000) ceased reporting NIAs. Conversely, nation-states that are committed to democracy report their NIAs, warts and all for example, Croatia or Nigeria and proto-states such as Montenegro or Kosovo, laying bare the economic policy issues that confront them.

According to Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development OECD (2021) Gross National Income (GNI) is defined as gross domestic product, plus net receipts from abroad of compensation of employees, property income and net taxes less subsidies on production. Compensation of employees receivable from abroad are those that are earned by residents who essentially live inside the economic territory but work abroad (this happens in border areas on a regular basis), or for people who live and work abroad for short periods (seasonal workers) and whose centre of economic interest remains in their home country. Property income receivable from/payable to abroad includes interest, dividends, and all (or part of) retained earnings of foreign enterprises owned fully (or in part) by resident enterprises (and vice versa). This indicator is based on GNI at current prices and is available in different measures: US dollars and US dollars per capita (both in current PPPs). All OECD countries compile their data according to the 2008 System of National Accounts (SNA). This indicator is less suited for comparisons over time, as developments are not only caused by real growth, but also by changes in prices and PPPs (OECD, 2021).

According to Britannica (2021), **national income accounting**, a set of principles and methods used to measure the income and production of a country. There are basically two ways of measuring national economic activity: as the money value of the total production of goods and services during a given period (usually a year) or as the total of incomes derived from economic activity after allowance has been made for capital consumption. The most commonly used indicator of national output is the gross national product (GNP), which is a measure of the total market value of currently produced finished goods and the value of services rendered. Because national output includes goods and services that are highly diverse in nature and some that are not in fact placed on the market, the determination of market value is difficult and somewhat imprecise. Nonetheless the use of a common basis of valuation makes it possible to obtain a total that fairly represents the level of output of a country. The rule that only currently produced goods and services should be counted ensures that only production occurring in the course of a given year is included and that any transaction in which money changes hands but no good or service does so in return (so-called transfer payments, *e.g.*, unemployment or social-security payments, gifts) is excluded. The rule that only finished or final goods must be counted is necessary to avoid double or triple counting of raw materials, intermediate products, and final products. For example, the value of automobiles already includes the value of the steel, glass, rubber, and other components that have been used to make

them.

The national income of any nation may be derived from the GNP by making allowances for certain non-income costs included in the GNP, mainly the costs of indirect taxes, subsidies, and the consumption of fixed capital (depreciation) (Britannica, 2021). National income thus calculated represents the aggregate income of the owners of the factors of production; it is the sum of wages, salaries, profits, interest, dividends, rent, and so on. The data accumulated for calculating the GNP and national income may be manipulated in a number of ways to show various relationships in the economy. Common uses of the data include: breakdowns of the GNP or the closely related GDP (gross domestic product) according to types of product or according to functional stages in its generation; breakdowns of national income by type of income; and analyses of the sources of financing (depreciation; savings by individuals, corporations, or institutions; and national deficits) (Britannica, 2021).

According to Australian Bureau of Statistics, a variety of measures of national income and output are used in economics to estimate total economic activity in a country or region, including gross domestic product (GDP), gross national product (GNP), net national income (NNI), and adjusted national income (NNI adjusted for natural resource depletion which is also called as NNI at factor cost). All are specially concerned with counting the total amount of goods and services produced within the economy and by various sectors. The boundary is usually defined by geography or citizenship, and it is also defined as the total income of the nation and also restrict the goods and services that are counted. For instance, some measures count only goods & services that are exchanged for money, excluding bartered goods, while other measures may attempt to include bartered goods by imputing monetary values to them.

Nigeria National Income

The World Bank has said Nigeria's economy is projected to grow by 2.4 per cent in 2021 (tradingeconomics.com). This is an increase in the bank's earlier growth projection of 1.8 per cent made in January this year (2021). The bank made this disclosure in the new edition of its Africa's Pulse report titled 'Climate change adaption and economic transformation in Sub-Saharan Africa'. According to the report, the projected growth in Nigeria is driven by growth in the service sectors of the economy. "Within Africa, recovery is also multi-speed. Angola, Nigeria, and South Africa, the largest economies in the region, are expected to emerge from the 2020 recession, yet at different paces. Angola is expected to grow by 0.4 per cent in 2021, after five consecutive years of recession. The country is still battling to gain momentum, with elevated debt levels and weak performance of the oil industry. Nigeria is expected to grow by 2.4 per cent in 2021, supported by the service sector (tradingeconomics.com).

The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) has been conducting Establishment Surveys to provide data for the estimation of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) for the country. In 2008, National Bureau of Statistics started to improve the Gross Domestic Product GDP series by conducting Quarterly Establishment Surveys (QES) for the four quarters of each year to complement the annual surveys which normally take place in the first quarter of the succeeding year (NBS, 2021). In 2018, the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) conducted the Quarterly Establishment Surveys for the first three quarters of 2018 (Q1-Q3/ 2018), while the fourth quarter survey for 2018, the first, second and third quarter survey for 2019 were conducted in

2019. Moreover, the fourth quarter survey for 2019, first and second quarter survey of 2020 were conducted in 2020. These surveys produced the data that was used for the compilation of the quarterly GDP for the four quarters of 2018 (Q1 – Q4, 2018), the four quarters of 2019 (Q1 – Q4, 2019), the first and second quarter of 2020 (Q1-Q2, 2020) (NBS, 2021).

Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) decreased by – 6.10%(year-on-year) in real terms in the second quarter of 2020, ending the 3-year trend of low but positive real growth rates recorded since the 2016/17 recession (NBS, 2021). The decline was largely attributable to significantly lower levels of both domestic and international economic activity during the quarter, which resulted from nationwide shutdown efforts aimed at containing the COVID-19 pandemic. The domestic efforts ranged from initial restrictions of human and vehicular movement implemented in only a few states to a nationwide curfew, bans on domestic and international travel, closure of schools and markets etc., affecting both local and international trade (NBS, 2021). The efforts, led by both the Federal and State governments, evolved over the course of the quarter and persisted throughout. When compared with Q2 2019, which recorded a growth of 2.12%, the Q2 2020 growth rate indicates a drop of – 8.22% points, and a fall of –7.97% points when compared to the first quarter of 2020 (1.87%). Consequently, for the first half of 2020, real GDP declined by – 2.18% year on year, compared with 2.11% recorded in the first half of 2019. Quarter on quarter, real GDP decreased by – 5.04% (NBS, 2021).

Furthermore, only 13 activities recorded positive real growth compared to 30 in the preceding quarter. In the quarter under review, aggregate GDP stood at N34,023,197.60 million in nominal terms, or -2.8% lower than the second quarter of 2019 which recorded an aggregate of N35,001,877.95 million. Overall, the nominal growth rate was –16.81% points lower than recorded in the second quarter of 2019, and –14.81% points lower than recorded in the first quarter of 2020. For better clarity, the Nigerian economy has been classified broadly into the oil and non-oil sectors (NBS, 2021). In the second quarter of 2020, an average daily oil production of 1.81 million barrels per day (mbpd) was recorded (NBS, 2021). This was - 0.21mbpd lower than the daily average production of 2.02mbpd recorded in the same quarter of 2019, and – 0.26mbpd lower than the first quarter 2020 production volume of 2.07mbpd. Real growth of the oil sector was – 6.63% (year-on-year) in Q2 2020 indicating a decrease of –13.80% points relative to the rate recorded in the corresponding quarter of 2019. Growth decreased by –11.69% points when compared to Q1 2020 which recorded 5.06%. Quarter-on-Quarter, the oil sector recorded a growth rate of –10.82% in Q2 2020. The Oil sector contributed 8.93% to total real GDP in Q2 2020, down from figures recorded in the corresponding period of 2019 and the preceding quarter, where it contributed 8.98% and 9.50% respectively (NBS, 2021).

According to National Bureau of Statistic NBS (2021), the non-oil sector declined by –6.05% in real terms during the reference quarter (Q2 2020). It was the first decline in real non-oil GDP growth rate since Q3 2017. The recorded growth rate was –7.70% points lower compared to the rate recorded during the same quarter of 2019, and –7.60% points compared to the first quarter of 2020. Nevertheless, non-oil sector output was driven by Financial and Insurance (Financial Institutions), Information and Communication (Telecommunications), Agriculture (Crop Production), and Public Administration, moderating the economy-wide decline. On the other hand, sectors which experienced the highest negative growth included Transport and Storage, Accommodation and Food Services, Construction, Education, Real

estate and Trade among others (NBS, 2021). In real terms, the Non-Oil sector accounted for 91.07% of aggregate GDP in the second quarter of 2020, slightly higher than the share recorded in the second quarter of 2019 (91.02%) as well as the first quarter of 2020 (90.50%) (NBS, 2021).

Real GDP in the Mining and Quarrying sector decreased by – 6.60% (year-on-year) in the second quarter of 2020. Compared to the same quarter of 2019 and first quarter 2020, it was lower by -13.60% points and –11.18% points respectively. Quarter on quarter, growth rate recorded was –9.66%, which means value added in second quarter 2020 was lower than in first quarter 2020. The contribution of Mining and Quarrying to real GDP in the quarter under review stood at 9.08%, lower than the rate of 9.12% recorded in the corresponding quarter of 2019 and the 9.54% recorded in the first quarter of 2020 respectively (NBS, 2021). Four sub-activities make up the Agricultural sector: Crop Production, Livestock, Forestry and Fishing. The sector grew by 19.90% year-on-year in nominal terms in Q2 2020, showing an increase of 2.14% points from the same quarter of 2019. Looking at the preceding quarter's growth rate of 22.47%, this quarter's growth rate represented a decline of –2.57% points. Crop Production remained the major growth driver of the sector, as it accounted for 87.34% of nominal GDP in the sector in Q2 2020. Quarter on Quarter, growth stood at 9.36% in the second quarter of 2020. Agriculture contributed 23.92% to nominal GDP, higher than the rates recorded for the second quarter of 2019 and the first quarter of 2020 which recorded 19.39% and 20.88% respectively (NBS, 2021).

According to Punch Newspaper (2021), Nigeria and South Africa still lagged behind in the projected growth for the Sub-Saharan region. The newspaper reported that according to the Central Bank of Nigeria's report; excluding South Africa and Nigeria, the rest of Sub-Saharan Africa is rebounding faster, with a growth rate of 3.6 per cent in 2021. It added, “Nigeria's economic growth shows little sign of speedy recovery from the 2020 recession. The economy grew five per cent in the second quarter, from 0.5 per cent growth in the first quarter. This was the third consecutive quarter of positive growth since the pandemic crisis. The main driver of the recovery is the non-oil sector, with a growth rate of 6.7 per cent compared with 0.8 per cent in the first quarter. The service sector recovered strongly after a disappointing first quarter, rising from -0.39 per cent to 9.27 per cent in the second quarter, while agriculture contracted from 2.28 in the first quarter to 1.30 per cent. Industrial activity also declined to -1.23 per cent in 2021Q2, down from 0.94 per cent in 2021Q1. Recent improvements in the labour markets have been largely attributed to workers turning to small-scale, nonfarm enterprise activities in retail and trade although their incomes remain precarious. In the first half of 2021, the fiscal deficit widened at four per cent of GDP, driven by an increase in debt servicing costs and capital expenditure. The Sub-Saharan region is projected to grow by 3.3 per cent in 2021, which is a percentage point higher than the forecast in April 2021 Africa's Pulse projection, 3.5 per cent in 2022, and 3.8 per cent in 2023. This rebound was fuelled by elevated commodity prices, relaxation of stringent measures, and recovery in global trade,” the report stated. The Central Bank, however, warned that although Sub-Saharan Africa was exiting recession in 2021, the recovery growth was still fragile, suggesting faster vaccine development to accelerate growth above five per cent for 2022.

The report of the Central Bank read, “Growth in economic activity for the region is projected at 3.5 per cent in 2022 and 3.8 per cent in 2023. “However, these projections are subject to substantial uncertainty around the pace of vaccination. Faster vaccine deployment

would accelerate growth to 5.1 per cent in 2022 and 5.4 per cent in 2023 in Sub-Saharan Africa – as containment measures are lifted faster than in the baseline and spending increases.” It added that in contrast, slower vaccine delivery and coverage would impede the relaxation of COVID-19 disruptions in economic activity and project growth to slow down to 2.4 per cent in 2023 (Punch Newspaper, 2021).

Importance of National Income

According to vedantu.com, there are several importance or reasons why nations do calculate

1. **Setting Economic Policy:** National Income indicates the status of the economy and can give a clear picture of the country's economic growth. National Income statistics can help economist in formulating economic policies for economic development.
2. **Inflation and Deflationary Gaps:** For timely anti-inflationary and deflationary policies, we need aggregate data of national income. If expenditure increases from the total output, it shows inflammatory gaps and vice versa.
3. **Budget Preparation:** Budget of the country is highly dependent on the net national income and its concepts. The Government formulates the yearly budget with the help of national income statistics in order to avoid any cynical policies.
4. **Standard of Living:** National income data assists the government in comparing the standard of living amongst countries and people living in the same country at different time.
5. **Defence and Development:** National income estimates help us to bifurcate the national product between defence and development purposes of the country. From such figures, we can easily know how much can be set aside for the defence budget.

Estimation Techniques of National Income

According to vedantu.com, there are four methods of measuring national income. Which method is to be used depends on the availability of data in a country and the purpose in hand.

1. **Income Method:** This method we add net income payments received by all citizens of a country in a particular year. Net incomes that result to all the factor of production like net rents, wages, interest, and profits are all added together, but income received in the form of transfer payments is omitted.
2. **Product Method:** According to this method, the aggregate value of final goods and services produced in a country during a financial year is computed at market prices. To find out GNP, the data of all the productive activities-agricultural products, Minerals, Industrial products, the contributions to production made by transport, insurance, communication, lawyers, doctors, teachers. Etc are accumulated and assessed.
3. **Expenditure Method:** The total expenditure by the society in a financial year is summed up together and includes personal consumption expenditure, net domestic investment, government expenditure on goods and services, and net foreign investment. This concept is backed by the assumption that national income is equal to national expenditure.

4. Value Added Method: The distinction between the value of material outputs and material inputs at every stage of production is Value added.

According to toppr.com, There are three ways of measuring the National Income of a country. They are from the income side, the output side and the expenditure side. Thus, we can classify these perspectives into the following methods of measurement of National Income. Methods of Measuring National Income are; Product Method, Income Method and Expenditure Method.

1. **Product Method:** Under this method, we add the values of output produced or services rendered by the different sectors of the economy during the year in order to calculate the National Income. In this method, we include only the value added by each firm in the production process in the output figure. Hence, we use the value-added method. The value-added output of all the sectors of the economy is the GNP at factor cost. However, this method is unscientific as it adds the value of only those goods and services that are sold in the market or are available for sale in the market.

2. **Income Method:** Under this method, we add all the incomes from employment and ownership of assets before taxation received from all the production activities in an economy. Thus, it is also the Factor Income method. We also need to add the undistributed profits of the private sector and the trading surplus of the public sector corporations. However, we need to exclude items not arising from productive activities such as sickness benefits, interest on the national debts, etc.

3. **Expenditure Method:** This method measures the total domestic expenditure of the economy. It consists of two elements, viz. Consumption expenditure and Investment expenditure (toppr.com).

METHODOLOGY

The data for this study was obtained from only secondary source. The nature of the data which are used by the researcher for this study is a published secondary data. Secondary sources of data include; texts, statistics data, journals, textbooks, internet texts, and government publications. The researcher for the purpose of literature review has obtained secondary data from existing sources such as books, journals, the internet and textbooks. Data collected from published materials or sources are analysed theoretically and descriptively in accordance to the key variable of the study.

Study Area

The study used secondary data concentrating on Nigeria's national income and the various estimated techniques adopted for calculating and analysis such income. Nigeria, an African country on the Gulf of Guinea, has many natural landmarks and wildlife reserves. Protected areas such as Cross River National Park and Yankari National Park have waterfalls, dense rainforest, savanna and rare primate habitats. One of the most recognizable sites is Zuma Rock, a 725m-tall monolith outside the capital of Abuja that's pictured on the national currency (Wikipedia.com). Nigeria officially the Federal Republic of Nigeria, is a country in West Africa. It is the most populous country in Africa; geographically situated between the Sahel to the north, and the Gulf of Guinea to the south in the Atlantic Ocean; covering an area of 923,769 square kilometres (356,669 sq mi), with a population of over 211 million. Nigeria

borders Niger in - the north, Chad in the northeast, Cameroon in the east, and Benin in the west. Nigeria is a federal republic comprising 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory, where the capital, Abuja is located. The largest city in Nigeria is Lagos, one of the largest metropolitan areas in the world and the second-largest in Africa (Wikipedia.com).

Nigeria has been home to several indigenous pre-colonial states and kingdoms since the second millennium BC, with the Nok civilization in the 15th century BC marking the first internal unification in the country (Breunig, 2014). The modern state originated with British colonization in the 19th century, taking its present territorial shape with the merging of the Southern Nigeria Protectorate and Northern Nigeria Protectorate in 1914 by Lord Lugard. The British set up administrative and legal structures while practising indirect rule through traditional chief system (Achebe, 2016). Nigeria became a formally independent federation on October 1, 1960. It experienced a civil war from 1967 to 1970, followed by a succession of democratically-elected civilian governments and military dictatorship, until achieving a stable democracy in the 1999 presidential election; the 2015 election was the first time an incumbent president had lost re-election (Akinbode, 2019).

Nigeria is a multinational state inhabited by more than 250 ethnic groups speaking 500 different languages, all identifying with a wide variety of cultures (Nicole, Breunig, and Kahlheber, 2008). The three largest ethnic groups are the —Hausa-Fulani in the north, Yoruba in the west, and Igbo in the east, together comprising over 60% of the total population (Breunig, 2014). The official language is English, chosen to facilitate linguistic unity at the national level (Pereltsvaig, 2011). Nigeria's constitution ensures freedom of religion and it is home to some of the world's largest Muslim and Christian populations, simultaneously (Achebe, 2016). Nigeria is divided roughly in half between Muslims, who live mostly in the north, and Christians, who live mostly in the south; ingenious religions, such as those native to the Igbo and Yoruba ethnicities, are in the minority.

According to Pereltsvaig (2011), Nigeria's economy is the largest in Africa, the 27th largest in the world by nominal GDP, and 25th largest by PPP. Nigeria is often referred to as the Giant of Africa owing to its large population and economy and is considered to be an emerging market by the World Bank (Akinbode, 2019). It is a regional power in Africa, a middle power in international affairs, and is an emerging global power. However, the country ranks very low in the Human Development Index and remains one of the most corrupt nations in the world. Nigeria is a founding member of the African Union and a member of many international organizations, including the United Nations, the Commonwealth of Nations, NAM, the Economic Community of West African States, and OPEC is also a member of the informal MINT group of countries and is one of the Next Eleven economies (Pereltsvaig, 2011).

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of published or secondary data shows that there are various types of estimation techniques adopted for Nigeria's national income evaluation. Findings from Uzonwanne, (2018) show that there are three distinct methods of estimating national income in Nigeria: GDP/GNP expenditure or product approach, GDP/GNP income or earning approach and GDP/GNP value added or output approach.

- **GDP/GNP Expenditure Approach**

This approach, also known as the GDP/GNP spending-based for a given year is calculated by adding up the spending going to purchase the final output produced in that year. Total spending on final output is expressed in the national accounts as the sum of three broad categories of spending: consumption investment and net exports. However, consumption is further divided into government consumption and that of private individuals (and non-profit organisations serving households).

This method is subdivided into other methods for calculating and evaluating GDP/GNP expenditure. These methods are:

Private Consumption Expenditure - private consumption expenditure includes spending by individuals on goods and services produced and sold to their final users during the year. It includes services such as haircut, medical care and legal advice, non-durable goods, such as fresh meat, clothing, cut flowers, and fresh vegetables and durable goods such as cars, television sets and microwave ovens. However, it excludes purchase of newly built houses as these are counted as investment.

Government Consumption Spending – when government provide goods and services that their citizens want, such as health care and street lighting, it is obvious that they are adding to the sum total of valuable output in the same way as do private firms that produce cars and video cassettes. With other government activities, the case may not seem so clear.

Investment Spending – investment spending as refer to as private investment or private domestic investment is defined as spending on the production of goods not for present consumption but rather for future use. The goods that arc created by this spending are called investment (or capital) goods. Investment spending can be divided into three categories; change in inventories, fixed capital formation and the net acquisition of valuables.

Gross and Net investment - total investment spending is called gross investment or gross capital formation. Gross investment is divided into two parts; replacement investment and net investment. Replacement investment is the amount of investment that just maintains the level of existing capital stock. In other words, it replaces the bits that have worn out.

Net Exports - The fourth category of aggregate spending and one that is very important to every economy arises from foreign trade. This is concerned with how imports and exports affect the calculation of GDP/GNP.

Total Spending – The GDP spending-based is therefore the sum of private consumption, government consumption, investment, and net exports spending on currently produced goods and services. It is GDP at market prices.

- **GDP/GNP INCOME APPROACH**

The production of a nation's output generates income. Labour must be employed, land must be rented, and capital must be used. The calculation of GDP/GNP from the income side involves adding up factor incomes so that all of that value is accounted for. National income accountants distinguish four main categories of factor incomes: operating surplus, compensation of employees, consumption of fixed capital, and indirect taxes less subsidies.

Operating Surplus - Operating surplus are net business incomes after payment has been made to hired labour and for material inputs but before direct taxes (such as company tax) have been paid. Operating surpluses are in large part profits of firms, but also included is the financial

surplus of organization other than companies such as universities. Both distributed and undistributed profits are included in the calculation of GDP/GNP.

Compensation of Employees – This is wages and salaries (usually just referred to as wages). It is the payment for the services of labour. In total, wages represent that part of the value of production that is attributable to hired labour.

Consumption of Fixed Capital – This is represented by net interest payments. Net interest includes interest earned by households and governments minus interest paid by households and governments. That is, interest paid by households and governments is excluded from the GDP/GNP because not all borrowing by government and consumers is for the acquisition of capital assets as schools, highways, automobiles, and household goods.

Indirect Taxes Less Subsidies – Subsidies and transfer payments are payments (including charitable contributions, bad debts) by the government and business sector to the household for which no current productive services are rendered. Hence, they are not included in the GDP/GNP. However, they are receipts of the household sector and therefore are included in personal income.

- **GDP/GNP VALUE ADDED OR OUTPUT APPROACH**

The most common method of measuring the national income is the value added or output approach. It measures the total output of goods and services. The reason why getting a total for the nation's output is not straightforward as it may seem at first sight, reason is that one firm's output may be another firm's input. Most modern manufactured products have many ready-made inputs. The total value of a firm's output is the gross value of its output. The firm's value added is the net value of its output. It is this latter figure that is the firm's contribution to the nation's total output. It is what its own efforts add to the value of what it takes in as inputs.

CONCLUSION

The study examines the estimated techniques of Nigeria national income. National income is the value of the aggregate output of the different sectors during a certain time period. In other words, it is the flow of goods and services produced in an economy in a particular year. Thus, the measurement of National Income becomes important. There are various techniques in measuring national income which include; product method, income method and expenditure method. In Nigeria, these methods are GDP/GNP Expenditure Approach, GDP/GNP Income Approach, and GDP/GNP Value Added or Output Approach as adopted by the Central Bank of Nigeria and the National Bureau of Statistic to calculate the national income of Nigeria on quarterly basis. The importance of calculating the national income of Nigeria cannot be over emphasized as national budget, development policies, and planning are based on the national income. Reports have shown that the Nigerian economy is recovering after the accidental COVID -19 economic attacks.

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